

Direct Solution of Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations Using a One-Step Hybrid Block Method

Omagwu, S.¹, Kumleng, G.M² and Abah, S.O.¹

¹Department of Mathematics & Statistics
Kaduna Polytechnics,
Kaduna, Nigeria

²Department of Mathematics
University of Jos, Nigeria

Abstract

In this paper, a one-step block method of order 3 is presented for the direct solution of the general second order ordinary differential equations (ODEs). The continuous formulation of the method was generated through the idea of the collocation and interpolation of the power series approximate solution. As a one-step method, the block method enjoys the desirable properties of the one step methods. The main properties of the method like the order, consistency and zero-stability were all examined in block form. The block method was found to be convergent as it is both consistent and zero-stable. The accuracy of the block method was tested on 3 second order ODEs and results obtained were compared with some existing methods in the literature.

Keywords: Power series, Approximate solution, Block method, One-step, Direct solution

1. Introduction

This paper focuses on the direct numerical solution of the general second order initial value problem of the form

$$y'' = f(x, y, y'), y(x_0) = y_0, y'(x_0) = y'_0, x = [a, b] \quad (1)$$

where f is continuous in the interval $[a, b]$. In the past, the solution to (1) was done by first reducing it to system of first order ordinary differential equations and then any good numerical method is used for the solution of the resulting system of ordinary differential equations. Scholars who worked on this old method of solving (1) include; (Brujnano & Trigiante, 1998; Vigo-Aguiar & Ramos, 2006). This old approach has its setbacks as it requires the development of separate sub-program for the starting values and functions arising from the system and also reduces the accuracy of the method as it computes numerical solution of the ordinary differential equation at one point at a time. (Adesanya et al 2009 and Omar & Kuboye, 2015). Monday (2016) reported also that this old method is computationally cumbersome and requires longer time and space to compute. It was

also observed by Vigo-Aguiar & Ramos (2006) that the old approach does not utilize additional information associated with a specific ordinary differential equation such as oscillatory nature of the solution. However, (Brown,1997) reported that the direct method of solving (1) is more efficient than the old approach. In order to stave off these drawbacks and to attain efficiency and accuracy, some scholars like (Yahaya & Badmus, 2009, Majid et al 2012, Areo et al, 2020) developed methods for solving (1) directly. One step methods have some advantages over the multistep methods and as such many scholars have developed one step block methods for the direct solution of (1) for example, Anake, Awoyemi & Adesanya (2012) constructed a zero-stable continuous implicit one-step method. The construction of a convergent one step block method for solving (1). (see Abdelrahim & Omar 2016). Skwame et al (2019) developed a one-step block method with equidistant for the solution of (1) using interpolation and collocation.

In an attempt to greatly improve on the accuracy of the existing methods, this paper introduces a new efficient one step block method that is consistent and zeros-table and as such convergent for the direct solution of the general second order ordinary differential equations. The performance of the new block method shall be compared with some existing ones in the literature.

2. Development of the Method

Consider a power series as an approximate solution to (1) in the form

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k \alpha_j x^j \tag{2}$$

where $k = 1$.

Differentiating (2) twice gives

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k j(j-1)\alpha_j x^{j-2} \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) is then equated to (1) to obtain

$$y''(x) = \sum_{j=0}^k j(j-1)\alpha_j x^{j-2} = f(x, y, y') \tag{4}$$

Interpolating (2) at $x = x_n, x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}$ and $x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}$ and collocating (3) $x = x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}$ and $x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}$ gives a system of nonlinear equation of the form

$$AX = U \tag{5}$$

where

$$A = [a_1 \ a_2 \ a_3 \ a_4 \ a_5]^T, \quad U = [y_n \ y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} \ y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \ f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} \ f_{n+\frac{2}{3}}]^T \text{ and}$$

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & x_n & x_n^2 & x_n^3 & x_n^4 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{1}{3}} & x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}^4 \\ 1 & x_{n+\frac{2}{3}} & x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}^2 & x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}^3 & x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}^4 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+\frac{1}{3}} & 12x_{n+\frac{1}{3}}^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 6x_{n+\frac{2}{3}} & 12x_{n+\frac{2}{3}}^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solving (5) for the unknowns a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 and substituting these values into (2) gives a continuous hybrid linear multistep method of the form

$$y(x) = \alpha_0(x)y_n + \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}(x)y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}(x)y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + h^2 \left(\beta_{\frac{1}{3}}(x)f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}(x)f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha_0(x), \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}(x), \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}(x), \beta_{\frac{1}{3}}(x), \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}(x)$ are all expressed in terms of $\tau = x - x_n$ as follows:

$$\alpha_0(\tau + x_n) = \frac{1}{2h^4} (2h^4 - 27h^3\tau + 108h^2\tau^2 - 162h\tau^3 + 81\tau^4)$$

$$\alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}(\tau + x_n) = \frac{3\tau}{h^4} (8h^3 - 36h^2\tau + 54h\tau^2 - 27\tau^3)$$

$$\alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}(\tau + x_n) = -\frac{3\tau}{2h^4} (7h^3 - 36h^2\tau + 54h\tau^2 - 27\tau^3)$$

$$\beta_{\frac{1}{3}}(\tau + x_n) = \frac{\tau}{18h^2} (16h^3 - 90h^2\tau + 153h\tau^2 - 81\tau^3)$$

$$\beta_{\frac{2}{3}}(\tau + x_n) = \frac{\tau}{18h} (2h^2 - 9h\tau + 9\tau^2)$$

Evaluating (6) at $\tau = h$ gives the following scheme

$$y_{n+1} = y_n - 3y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 3y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} - \frac{h^2}{9} f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \frac{h^2}{9} f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (7)$$

Differentiating (6) yields

$$y'(x) = \alpha_0'(x)y_n + \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}'(x)y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}'(x)y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + h^2 \left(\beta_{\frac{1}{3}}'(x)f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}'(x)f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \right) \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_0'(\tau + x_n) &= -\frac{27}{2h^4}(h^3 - 8h^2\tau + 18h\tau^2 - 12\tau^3) \\ \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}'(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{6}{h^4}(4h^3 - 36h^2\tau + 81h\tau^2 - 54\tau^3) \\ \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}'(\tau + x_n) &= -\frac{3}{2h^4}(7h^3 - 72h^2\tau + 162h\tau^2 - 108\tau^3) \\ \beta_{\frac{1}{3}}'(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{1}{18h^2}(16h^3 - 180h^2\tau + 459h\tau^2 - 324\tau^3) \\ \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}'(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{1}{18h}(2h^2 - 18h\tau + 27\tau^2)\end{aligned}$$

Evaluating (8) at $\tau = 0, \frac{1}{3}h, \frac{2}{3}h$ and h yields the following

$$18y'_n = \frac{16}{h^2}f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 2h^2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} - 243y_n + 432y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 189y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (9)$$

$$18hy'_{n+\frac{1}{3}} = -5h^2f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - h^2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + 27y_n - 108y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 81y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (10)$$

$$18hy'_{n+\frac{2}{3}} = 4h^2f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 2h^2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} - 27y_n + 27y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (11)$$

$$18hy'_{n+1} = -29h^2f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 11h^2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + 243y_n - 540y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + 297y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (12)$$

Next, (8) is differentiated to arrive at

$$y''(x) = \alpha_0''(x)y_n + \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}''(x)y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}''(x)y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + h^2\left(\beta_{\frac{1}{3}}''(x)f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}''(x)f_{n+\frac{2}{3}}\right) \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_0''(\tau + x_n) &= -\frac{27}{2h^4}(-8h^2 + 36h\tau - 36\tau^2) \\ \alpha_{\frac{1}{3}}''(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{6}{h^4}(-36h^2 + 162h\tau - 162\tau^2) \\ \alpha_{\frac{2}{3}}''(\tau + x_n) &= -\frac{3}{2h^4}(-72h^2 + 324h\tau - 324\tau^2) \\ \beta_{\frac{1}{3}}''(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{1}{18h^2}(-180h^2 + 918h\tau - 972\tau^2) \\ \beta_{\frac{2}{3}}''(\tau + x_n) &= \frac{1}{18h}(-18h + 54\tau)\end{aligned}$$

Evaluating (13) at $\tau = h$ gives

$$h^2 f_{n+1} = -13h^2 f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 2h^2 f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} - 108y_n + 216y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 108y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} \quad (14)$$

The new block method is obtained by combining (7), (9),(10),..., (14).

2.1 Modified Block Method

Following Fatunla(1995), the block method is modified so that the unknown parameters can be evaluated independently. The modified block method is given as

$$A^0 h^\lambda Y_m^{(n)} = h^\lambda \sum_{i=0}^k A^i Y_{m-i}^{(i)} + h^\mu \sum_{i=0}^k B^i F_{m-i}^{(i)} \quad (15)$$

where n is the power of the derivative, μ is the order of the differential equation. A^0 and $A^{(i)}$ are $R \times R$ identity matrices and λ is the power of h relative to the derivative of the differential equation, where

$$h^\lambda Y_m^{(n)} = \left[y_{n+\frac{1}{3}}, y_{n+\frac{2}{3}}, \dots, y_{n+1}, \dots, hy'_{n+\frac{1}{3}}, \dots, hy'_{n+1}, \dots, h^2 y'_{n+\frac{1}{3}}, \dots, h^2 y'_{n+1}, \dots, h^2 y''_{n+\frac{2}{3}}, \dots, h^2 y''_{n+1}, \dots, h^n y^n_{n+m} \right]^T$$

$$h^\lambda Y_{m-i}^{(n)} = \left[y_{n-1}, y_{n-2}, \dots, y_n, \dots, hy'_{n-1}, \dots, hy'_n, \dots, h^2 y'_{n-1}, h^2 y'_{n-2}, \dots, h^m y^m_n \right]^T$$

$$F_{m-i} = \left[f_{n-\frac{1}{3}}, f_{n-\frac{2}{3}}, f_{n-1}, \dots, f_m, \dots, f_{n+\frac{1}{3}}, f_{n+\frac{2}{3}}, f_{n+1}, \dots, f_m \right]^T$$

Evaluating equations (7), (9),(10),... (14) for $h^\lambda y_{n+m}^\lambda$, $m = 0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, 1$, gives

$$A^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$A^i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{1}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$B^i = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{5}{8} & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{8} \\ \frac{1}{8} & -\frac{11}{108} & \frac{7}{216} \\ \frac{10}{27} & -\frac{2}{9} & \frac{2}{27} \\ \frac{3}{4} & 0 & \frac{1}{4} \\ \frac{23}{36} & -\frac{4}{9} & \frac{5}{36} \\ \frac{7}{9} & -\frac{2}{9} & \frac{1}{9} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Substituting (16), (17) and (18) into equation (15) gives the hybrid block method

$$y_{n+1} = hy'_n + y_n + \frac{h^2}{8} \left(5f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + f_{n+1} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$y_{n+\frac{1}{3}} = y_n + \frac{1}{3}hy'_n + \frac{h^2}{216} \left(27f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 22f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + 7f_{n+1} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$y_{n+\frac{2}{3}} = y_n + \frac{2}{3}hy'_n + \frac{2h^2}{27} \left(5f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 3f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + f_{n+1} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$y'_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{h}{4} \left(3f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} + f_{n+1} \right) \quad (22)$$

$$y'_{n+\frac{1}{3}} = y_n + \frac{h}{36} \left(23f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 16f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + 5f_{n+1} \right) \quad (23)$$

$$y'_{n+\frac{2}{3}} = y_n + \frac{h}{9} \left(7f_{n+\frac{1}{3}} - 2f_{n+\frac{2}{3}} + f_{n+1} \right) \quad (24)$$

The modified block method is obtained from the combination of (19), ..., (24).

3. Analysis of the Method

The basic properties of the block method above which include the order, zero stability and convergence shall be investigated here.

3.1 Order of the block

The method by Fatunla (1995), and Lambert (1973) was used in obtaining the order of our block method (19)...(24) as $(3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3)^T$ with error constant of $\left(\frac{-13}{3240}, \frac{-97}{87480}, \frac{-28}{10935}, \frac{-1}{216}, \frac{-1}{216}, \frac{-1}{243} \right)^T$

3.2 Zero-Stability

To obtain the zero stability of the block method we consider the following conditions:

(i) The block (15) is said to be stable if as $h \rightarrow 0$ the roots $r_j, j=1..k$ of the first characteristic polynomial $\rho(R)=0$, that is $\rho(R) = \det\left(\sum A^{(i)}R^{k-1}\right) = 0$, satisfy $|R| \leq 1$ and for those roots with $|R|=1$, must have multiplicity equal to unity. (See Fatunla(1995) for details).

(ii) If (15) is an $R \times R$ matrix then, it is zero stable if as $h^\mu \rightarrow 0, |RA^0 - A^i| = R^{r-\mu}(R-1) = 0$.

For those roots with $|R|=1$, the multiplicity must not exceed the order of the differential equation.

For the block method (19)...(24),

$$\lambda A^0 - A^i = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{1}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & \lambda & 0 & -1 & 0 & -\frac{1}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda & 0 & 0 & -\frac{2}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda-1 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \tag{25}$$

As $h \rightarrow 0$ in (15), ((25) reduces to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & \lambda & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda-1 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \tag{26}$$

The determinant of (26) yields the values $\lambda = 0, 1, 1$. Now, taking the determinant of (25) we have $\lambda^5(\lambda-1) = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda_1 = 1, \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5 = \lambda_6 = 0$

Hence, the block method is zero-stable since the two conditions above are satisfied. Therefore, the method is convergent since it is consistent and zero-stable.

4. Numerical Implementation

In this section, the new block method is used in solving three-second order initial value problems and results obtained are compared with some existing methods. Tables 1, 2 and 3 summarize the results obtained.

Problem 1

Consider the nonlinear initial value problem (I.V.P) which was solved by Awoyemi et al. (2011)

with $h = \frac{1}{320}$

$$y'' - x(y')^2 = 0, \quad y(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = \frac{1}{2}$$

Exact solution: $y(x) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{2+x}{2-x}\right)$

The results are shown in table 1 below for some selected points. The new method performs better than that of by Awoyemi et al. (2011) as can be seen from the table.

Table 1: Results of the new block method compared with Awoyemi et al. (2011)

x	Exact result $y(x)$	New result $yn(x)$	Error in new Method	Error in Awoyemi et al. (2011)
0.1	1.050041729279	1.050041729279	0.00	6.5501E-11
0.2	1.100335347731	1.100335347733	2.0000E-12	5.4803E-10
0.3	1.151140435937	1.151140435942	5.0000E-12	1.9256E-09
0.4	1.202732554054	1.202732554064	1.0000E-11	4.8029E-09
0.5	1.255412811883	1.255412811899	1.6000E-11	1.0006E-08
0.6	1.309519604203	1.309519604229	2.6000E-11	1.8727E-08
0.7	1.365443754271	1.365443754311	4.0000E-11	3.2746E-08
0.8	1.423648930194	1.423648930253	5.9000E-11	5.3969E-08
0.9	1.484700278594	1.484700278682	8.8000E-11	8.8004E-08
1.0	1.549306144334	1.549306144467	1.3300E-10	1.4353E-07

Problem 2: Consider the system

$$y_1'' = -e^{-x} y_2, \quad y_1(0) = 1, \quad y_1'(0) = 0, \quad h = 0.01$$

$$y_2'' = 2e^x y_1', \quad y_2(0) = 1, \quad y_2'(0) = 1$$

$$y_1(x) = \cos x, \quad y_2(x) = e^x \cos x$$

Table 2: Results of the new block method compared with Abdelrahim et al (2016)

x	Exact solution of y_1	Computed solution of y_1 for the new method	Error of y_1 for the new method	Error of y_1 in Abdelrahim et al (2016)
0.2	0.980066577841241630	0.9800665778358812840	5.360347×10^{-12}	3.348466×10^{-9}
0.4	0.921060994002884990	0.9210609939684610314	3.442405×10^{-11}	3.276545×10^{-8}
0.6	0.825335614909678110	0.8253356148132973326	9.638096×10^{-11}	1.332214×10^{-7}
0.8	0.69670670934716505	0.6967067091529559262	1.942095×10^{-10}	3.546280×10^{-7}
1.0	0.540302305868139210	0.5403023055365514675	3.315882×10^{-10}	7.355177×10^{-7}

Problem 3:

$$y'' = y', \quad y(0) = 0, \quad y'(0) = -1, \quad h = 0.1$$

Exact solution: $y(x) = 1 - e^x$

Table 3: Results of the new block method compared with Omar et al (2015) and Mohammed et al (2014)

x	Exact solution	Computed solution	Error in new Method (order p=3)	Error in Omar et al (2015) order p=6	Error in Mohammed et al (2014) Order p=5
0.1	-0.105170918076	-0.105170963016	4.4940E=08	2.508826E-13	2.004000000E-07
0.2	-0.221402758160	-0.221402909550	1.51390E-07	6.493175E-11	5.386000000E-07
0.3	-0.349858807576	-0.349859139365	3.31789E-07	1.683146E-09	8.840000000E-07
0.4	-0.491824697641	-0.491825298158	6.00517E-07	1.700635E-08	1.229700000E-06
0.5	-0.648721270700	-0.648722244856	9.74156E-07	1.025454E-07	1.575200000E-06
0.6	-0.822118800391	-0.822120272192	1.47180E-06	2.558711E-06	1.920400000E-06
0.7	-1.013752707470	-1.013754822875	2.11541E-06	5.273300E-06	2.506000000E-06
0.8	-1.225540928492	-1.225543858654	2.93016E-06	8.275935E-06	3.106000000E-06
0.9	-1.459603111157	-1.459607056111	3.94495E-06	1.161667E-05	3.705000000E-06
1.0	-1.718281828459	-1.718287021306	5.19285E-06	1.542187E-05	4.304000000E-06

It can be seen clearly from Table 1, that for problem 1 results from our new one step block method of order 3 performs better than that of Awoyemi et al. (2011) of a higher order (order 4). In Table 2, Again results from our one -step method of order 3 performs better than that of Abdelrahim et al (2016) of order 4 at some selected points. Finally in Table 3, the new method performs slightly better than that of Mohammed et al (2014) of order 5 while it competes well with that of Omar et al (2015) especially as one approaches the end of the interval.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the construction of a consistent, zero-stable and hence convergent one-step hybrid block method for the direct solution of the general second order ordinary differential has been achieved. The new one-step hybrid block method of order 3 has shown in Table 1,2 & 3 that it is superior to some methods that are of higher order than it in the literature.

References

- Adesanya, A. O., Anake, T. A., Bishop S. A. and Osilagun, J. A. (2009). Two steps block method for the solution of general second order initial value problems of ordinary differential equation, *Asset*, 8(1), 59-68.
- Abdelrahim, R. and Omar, Z. (2016). Direct Solution of Second-Order Ordinary Differential Equation Using a Single-Step Hybrid Block Method of Order Five, *Math. Comput. Appl.* 21,12.
- Anake, T. A., Awoyemi, D. O. and Adesanya, A. A. (2012). A One Step Method for the Solution of General Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations, *International Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(4), 159-163.
- Areo, E. A., Adeyanju, N. O. and Kayode, S. J. (2020). Direct Solution of Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations Using a Class of Hybrid Block Methods, *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5(2).
- Awoyemi, D. O., Adebile E. A., Adesanya, A. O. and Anake .T. A. (2011). Modified block method for the direct solution of second order ordinary differential equations, *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 3(3), 181-188.
- Badmus, A .M. and Y. A. Yahaya. (2009). An accurate uniform order 6 block method for direct solution of general second order ordinary differential equations, *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 10(2), 248-254.
- Brown, R. L. (1977), Some characteristic of implicit multistep derivative integration formulas, *SIAM J. Num. Anal.*, 14, 982-993.
- Brunjano, L. and Trigiante, D. (1998). *Solving Differential Problems by Multistep Initial and Boundary Value Methods*. Amsterdam, Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, Netherlands.

Fatunla, S. O. (1995). A class of block method for second order initial value problems. *International journal of computer mathematics*, 55(1 & 2), 119-133.

Lambert, J.D.(1973):*Computational methods in ordinary differential equation*, John Wiley,New York

Majid, Z. A., Mokhtar, N. Z. and Suleiman, M, (2012).Direct Two-Point Block One-Step Method for Solving General Second-Order Ordinary Differential Equations", *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2012, Article ID 184253, 16 pages, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/184253>

Mohammed, U.and Adeniyi, R.B. (2014). Derivation of block hybrid backward difference formula (HBDF) through multistep collocation for solving second order differential equations. *The PacificJournal of Science and Technology*, 15(3), 89 – 95.

Monday, K. D. (2016), An Accurate Five Off-Step Points Implicit Block Method for Direct Solution of Fourth Order Differential Equations, *Open Access Library Journal*, 3(6).

Omar,Z.andKuboye, J. O. (2015). A New Implicit Block Method for Solving Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations Directly,*Gazi University Journal of Science* 28(4), 689-694.

Skwame, Y., Sabo, J. and Mathew, M. (2019). The Treatment of Second Order Ordinary Differential Equations Using Equidistant One-step Block Hybrid. *Asian Journal of Probability and Statistics*, 5(3), 1-9.
<https://doi.org/10.9734/ajpas/2019/v5i330136>

Vigo-Aguiar, J. and Ramos, H. (2006) Variable Step Size Implementation of Multistep Method for $y'' = f(x, y, y')$.*Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, 192, 114-131
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cam.2005.04.043>

Wend, D. (1969). Existence and Uniqueness of solution of ordinary differential equation. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 23(1), 27-23

Yahaya, A.M. and Badmus, Y.A. (2009). An Accurate Uniform Order 6, Block Method for Direct Solution of General Second Order Ordinary Differential Equation. *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 10, 248-254.